

liwāt: Homosexuality or Buggery?

ARNO SCHMITT, Berlin

Abstract Translating *liwāt* as "homosexuality" is a category error. While "homosexuality" is a modern, diffuse concept spanning from disposition to sex acts, *liwāt* denotes the penile penetration of the anus. The overlap is minimal. While the modern concept has partnership at its core, *liwāt* is an asymmetrical act performed by a man, indifferent to the gender of the recipient (man, woman, boy, or eunuch). A valency analysis shows that these forms reflect an ontologically transitive reality; even in absolute use, they refer to a unilateral act performed by an agent upon a patient.

Résumé Traduire *liwāt* par « homosexualité » est une erreur de catégorie. Alors que l'homosexualité est un concept moderne et diffus, englobant tout de la disposition aux pratiques sexuelles, le *liwāt* désigne la pénétration anale par un homme. Le chevauchement est minimal. L'interprétation par Pierre Larcher des formes verbales III et V pour en déduire une réciprocité se heurte à la réalité. L'analyse de la valence démontre que ces formes reflètent une réalité ontologiquement transitive : même dans un emploi absolu, elles renvoient à un acte unilatéral accompli par un agent sur un patient (homme, femme, garçon ou eunuque). Le *liwāt* demeure un acte asymétrique.

Kurzfassung Die Übersetzung von *liwāt* als „Homosexualität“ ist ein Kategorienfehler. Während „Homosexualität“ ein diffuser Begriff ist, der von Disposition bis Praktiken alles Mögliche umschließt, bezeichnet *liwāt* die anale Penetration durch einen Mann. Die Überschneidung ist minimal. Während das moderne Konzept im Kern partnerschaftlich ist, ist *liwāt* ein asymmetrischer Akt, bei dem das Objekt ein Mann, eine Frau, ein Mädchen, ein Knabe oder ein Eunuch sein kann. Pierre Larchers Versuch, die Verben III und V reziprok zu lesen, scheitert. Eine Valenzanalyse zeigt, dass diese Verbformen eine ontologisch transitive Realität abbilden: Auch im absoluten Gebrauch referieren sie auf einen einseitigen Vollzug eines Agens an einem Patienten. Während das moderne Konzept im Kern partnerschaftlich ist, ist *liwāt* ein asymmetrischer Akt.

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For most of the time, *liwāt* has meant ‘sodomy’ — a meaning it has regained. However, before 2000 many Arabists took it to mean ‘homosexuality’. In 1983, LORENZ KROPFITSCH¹ glossed *liwāt/luwāt/liwāta* as “widernatürliche Unzucht, Sodomie, Päderastie, Homosexualität (unnatural intercourse, sodomy, pederasty, homosexuality).”

The problem is not the morally charged first term, but the last. The issue is not that “homosexuality” lacks a clear referent—what is “same-sex-ness” supposed to be?—but that it has accumulated a dozen meanings, none of which corresponds closely to sodomy/anal intercourse. “Sodomy” itself has covered a wider range of acts (e.g. in Thomas Aquinas: sexual acts with animals, demons, or oneself; 1900-50 in most states of the USA it included oral intercourse). *Liwāt* and sodomy are structurally similar; both originate in a sacred narratives and neither is self-explanatory: the scriptural story provides a point of origin, while later discourse determines which specific acts are denoted.

Over the past 150 years, “homosexuality” has been understood as: a) a mental illness, b) a disposition, c) an inclination, d) a perversion, e) a crime, f) a sexual preference, g) an inborn faculty, h) an aspect of adult personality, i) a latent impulse, j) an orientation, k) a shameful element of one’s personality, l) enacted impulses, m) arousal by a member of one’s sex, n) a mode of conduct, o) a form of sexual behaviour, p) a socio-political identity, q) a sexual orientation, r) a subcultural affiliation, s) a lifestyle, t) sex acts. Only at this last point is there any overlap with *liwāt*. While “homosexuality” refers to a wide range of practices (from kissing and cuddling to spanking), *liwāt* refers specifically to penile penetration of the anus, regardless of the sex or gender of of the person whose anus is penetrated.

¹ Only the first four editions (Wiesbaden, 1952-68, plus Bairut 1977) of “the Wehr” were compiled by Hans Wehr. The 5th, and 6th editions, although published under his name, were expanded by Lorenz Kropfisch; he added the gloss “Homosexualität”, and the vocalization *luwāt* in the morphological pattern of a disease term.

Thus, while the Arabic term denotes one specific act, the European concept can refer to a thousand different things—and to feelings, relations, dispositions, ... acts between women and between intersex persons. While *liwāṭ* is an **act** performed by **a man** upon **any** human, homosexuality may refer to an orientation, an inclination, a preference, a set of behaviour, or even a **social** phenomenon.

This I wrote in 1985 in German, in 1992 it was published in English and in 2001 in this Journal. I showed that *liwāṭ* is a specific act while the other a turpitude, a perversion, an attraction, a character trait, and I adduced textual evidence, that *liwāṭ* can be on a girl, a woman, a eunuch: clearly not same-sex. And it is not egalitarian gay, because jurists say, that there is no desire on the part of the “place” into which the penis is introduced. When KHALED EL-ROUAYHEB wrote *Before Homosexuality*, the question was no longer up for debate. I thought his book was the final nail in the coffin for translating *liwāṭ* as ‘homosexuality’.

So, Pierre LARCHER’s article on *liwāṭ* surprised me. He starts by declaring that (PELLAT’s²) article in EI² interprets *liwāṭ* as sodomy, which is conceptually wrong: the article translates the word with sodomy, but is about homosexuality (it covers *ubna* and *siḥāq*, *ḡulāmiyyāt* and *muḥannaṭūn*); Pellat treated a modern European subject under the name of an old Arabic term³.

Larcher claims that I have shown that in Islamic law (*fiqh*) *liwāṭ* denotes anal intercourse rather than male homosexuality. This is incorrect. I have never defined *liwāṭ* for Islamic law. My analysis concerns the Arabic language itself. I do not assume that the term has one meaning in *fiqh* and another in medicine, belles lettres, or everyday usage; the word denotes the same act across all registers. In the very article he cites (and distorts), there is in fact a section on “non-legal attestations,” which should have made this point unmistakable. The referential definition is: “what the people of Lot did:” the analytic definition: penile penetration of the anus (juridically: the insertion of the glans or an equivalent portion of the

² After the article signed “réd.” had appeared, I called Prof. Pellat to ask whether he was the principal or the sole author. He replied: “Je l’ai écrit tout seul.” Pellat and Brill allowed me to reprint it in the anthology, Sofer and I published.

³ in the article homosex occurs 19 times, sodomy 9x, twice perversion, depravity and deviant each, once hermaphrodite, ma’būn and vice six time each; *ḥulāq* and *ḥalaqī* never.

penis into the anus of a human being). And there is the predominant usage: anal penetration of a male being (boy, youth, man, eunuch, hermaphrodite, effeminate), which does not alter the definition, in which penetration of the anus of girls and women is included.

Finally, there is a metaphorical, moral extension in expressions such as “*liwāṭ* of the gaze” or “*liwāṭ* of the heart,” where the desire to penetrate someone anally is loosely labelled *liwāṭ*. This does not modify the core definition; the speaker does not imagine that one can penetrate with the eyes, but uses the term expansively without weakening its semantic nucleus

As the expert on the formation of verbs and their valency, LARCHER posits that *yālūṭu* (prefix-tense) preceded *lāṭa* (suffix-tense) (214), that *liwāṭ* is *maṣdar* to both *lāṭa* and *lāwāṭa* having served as the bridge between I and III (215f.), that *lūṭīyya* influenced *lūṭī* (223), that *lā`iṭ* (pl. *lāṭa*, *luwwāṭ* and *lā`iṭūna*), and *lawwāṭ* (pl. *lawwāṭūna* and *lawwāṭa*) are formed on *lāṭa* (I) (223). He suggests that *liwāṭ* emerged under the analogical pressure of *ḡimā`* (and *zinā`*⁴) — perhaps directly from the name Lūṭ. And he repeats his morphogenetic principle: Un verbe n’est jamais qu’un ensemble de formes. Un nouveau verbe commence toujours et nécessairement par l’une de ses formes./A verb is never just a set of forms. A new verb always and necessarily begins with one of its forms. (214)

LARCHER asks why *lāwāṭa* emerged: as a transitive alternative to an intransitive *lāṭa*? But must admit that both can be absolute, with accusative and with *bi* (215) and I add that both mean an asymmetrical action requiring an argument. While one can just **be** a stone or a sufi, one can not be a *lūṭī* without an object⁵, just as one can not eat without something to eat. As great as LARCHER is as a morphologist, I disagree with him on semantics. He suggests that *liwāṭ* and *lūṭīyya* refer to “homosexual sodomy” only (219), which is poorly phrased (he means male-male sodomy, not sodomy among women) and wrong: yes, like *ḡihad* mostly **refers** to military action, but **means** “effort, striving”, the definition of *liwāṭ* and its most common usage diverge.

⁴ and other *fi`āl* forms like *sifāḥ* and *ḥiḍān*.

⁵ *Lūṭī* and *ma`būn* are not complementary. The former refers to an act, regardless of motivation or frequency; the latter describes a desire to be penetrated anally that may never manifest in this world.

It simply means anal penetration of a human being, **can** refer to buggery of a girl or woman, a hermaphrodite or eunuch.

LARCHER does not understand the sexual logic of classical Arabic. When he writes “`ātin and *mu`tā* are commonly used to denote the two partners in a sexual relationship” (219) he uses the word partner, as if the murderer and his/her victim were partners in crime. Where a modern Scandinavian sees two men doing something together, the ancients saw one doing something to another.

On *talawwāṭa* he distorts my position⁶. That I say in the text “ist fast synonym zu *lāta bi* (is almost synonymous to)” and write in the footnote “Wäre *talawwāṭa* hier reziprok, brauchten, die Eunuchen nicht nach den *ḡilmān* zu verlangen, sie könnten ja miteinander *yatalawwāṭūn*./Were *talawwāṭa* reciprocal in meaning, the eunuchs could do it with each other without having to chase boys.” LARCHER passes over this altogether, devoting two pages to a suggestion in my note, that form V verbs can mean “to become X” and/or “to pretending to be X”. Although German “oder” is inclusive, he speculates: does SCHMITT mean become or pretend, as if the distinction were central to my argument. It is not. My point was simply that form V can express adoption of a role, whether genuinely or performatively, and that this has no bearing on the semantic valency of *talawwāṭa* in the passage under discussion.

The verb II does not exist and *al-lawwāṭ* which expresses a propensity (like *kaddāb*/liar and *nammām*/tale-bearer) is extremely rare in classic Arabic. Conversely, in this set of verbs, forms III and V, which often convey reciprocity, are merely doublets of form I, since here reciprocity is inconceivable – which does not mean that it never occurred, but simply that it was

⁶ and he attacks me for truncating a quotation. Yes, cut, but without altering the argument. He himself states “For Ḡāḥiḏ, a *ḥaṣī* is not effeminate at all, (but) sexually obsessed, with a homosexual preference.” (221 n.9 – again I ask: why not “a preference for males”?). On one occasion, Ḡāḥiḏ saw a non-*ḥaṣī* as obsessed with boys as most eunuchs are. And he suggests that I took the quote from Ullmann, ignoring that I submitted the paper long before the fascicle of WKAS appeared (Oct. 2020).

unthinkable and when it happened (behind closed doors and/or under the influence), it was not spoken of.⁷

Unfortunately, he imputes to me positions that my text does not support. “SCHMITT semble pencher en faveur du comportement affecté. ... Il hésite par suite sur le sens/ SCHMITT seems to lean in favor of the affected behavior. ... He hesitates as to meaning (220, 221)” Merely a conjecture. I leave it open, my “oder” is “or/and”, not exclusive..

More important, Larcher argues: “Et, cette activité se faisant à deux, cela suffit, me semble-t-il, à expliquer que ce verbe puisse se prédiquer de personnages, dont on suppose que, dans ladite action, ils tiennent, pour des raisons physiologiques ou psychologiques, le rôle du passif plutôt que de l’actif./ And since this activity is performed by two people, this seems to me sufficient to explain why the verb can be predicated of individuals who, for physiological or psychological reasons, are assumed to take the passive rather than the active role in the action in question.” The premise that the action necessarily involves two persons does not follow from the verb itself. The verb is ontologically transitive and can describe situations with multiple agents acting upon a single patient — including cases of collective assault. The number of agents is semantically irrelevant: the verb always encodes an asymmetric act performed by A (or A₁, A₂, A₃...) upon V, not a jointly performed or reciprocal activity.

Nothing in the semantics of the verb supports the idea that the active form could be predicated of the participant who undergoes the act: No instance is attested in which the object of the act functions as the active subject of a sentence with III (*lāwāṭa*) or V (*talawwāṭa*). On this basis, the further claim that the verb would be predicated “rather” of the passive participant is not merely unsupported; a form that is not used of the patient cannot be used **preferentially** of that participant. The appeal to unspecified ‘physiological’ or ‘psychological’ reasons adds no explanatory value; no such factors are identified, and nothing in the textual or cultural record suggests what these reasons might be or how they would justify a usage that is otherwise unattested.

⁷ I am convinced that the physical acts are not always and everywhere the same, but that different ideas about things sexual lead to different behaviours, but life is not identical to concepts about it.

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